

Data Files for Runoff Evaluation in an Earth System Land Model for Permafrost Regions

NGEE Arctic Record_id: NGA573

Summary:

Modeling of hydrological runoff is essential for accurately capturing spatiotemporal feedbacks within the land–atmosphere system, particularly in sensitive regions such as permafrost landscapes. However, substantial uncertainties persist in the terrestrial runoff parameterization schemes used in Earth system and land surface models. This is particularly true in permafrost regions, where landscape heterogeneity is high and reliable observational data are scarce. In this study, we evaluate the performance of runoff parameterization schemes in the Energy Exascale Earth System Model (E3SM) land model (ELM). Our proposed framework leverages simulation results from the Advanced Terrestrial Simulator (ATS), which is a physics-rich integrated surface/subsurface hydrologic model that has been successfully evaluated previously in Arctic tundra regions. We used ATS to simulate runoff from 22 representative hillslopes in the Sagavanirktok River basin, located on the North Slope of Alaska, then compared the output with ELM’s parameterized representation of total runoff. Results show that 1) ELM’s total runoff was the same order of magnitude as the ATS simulations, and both models were similarly variable over time; 2) minor adjustments to coefficients in ELM’s runoff parameterization improved the match between the ATS simulation and ELM’s parameterized representation of annual and seasonal total runoff; 3) overall, runoff responses in ATS and ELM are more similar in flat hillslope environments compared to steep hillslopes; and 4) shallower active layer thicknesses and higher precipitation simulations resulted in lower correlations between the two models due to greater total runoff. By incorporating the optimized runoff coefficients from the Sagavanirktok River basin into ELM, the simulated total runoff better matched the streamflow observations at a small watershed located on the Seward Peninsula of Alaska. Our findings revealed important insights into the effectiveness of runoff parameterizations in land surface models and pathways for improving runoff coefficients in typical Arctic regions.

This data set includes all files that were produced and applied in the paper, which is in review as of July 1 2025 in Geoscientific Model Development (GMD).

Please use this citation to reference the data.

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Related Publication:

Huang, X., Zhang, Y., Gao, B., Abolt, C. J., Crumley, R. L., Demir, C., Fiorella, R. P., Busey, B., Bolton, B., Painter, S. L., and K.E. Bennett: *Runoff Evaluation in an Earth System Land Model for Permafrost Regions, EGUsphere [preprint]*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-1753>, 2025. Submitted.

Related Datasets:

ERA5 forcing data to run the ELM model can be downloaded from the ECMWF Climate Data Store: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>.

ATS forcings data can be retrieved from Daymet version 4 dataset (Thornton et al., 2020).

Streamflow data was derived from Busey B; Wales N; Newman B; Wilson C; Bolton B (2019): Surface Water: Stage, Temperature and Discharge, Teller Road Mile Marker 27, Seward Peninsula, Alaska, beginning 2016-2021. Next Generation Ecosystem Experiments (NGEE) Arctic, ESSDIVE repository. Dataset. <https://doi.org/10.5440/1618330>. Streamflow data is also included in the Pangea repository (see above).

NGEE Arctic Project Summary

The Next-Generation Ecosystem Experiments: Arctic (NGEE Arctic), was a research effort to reduce uncertainty in Earth System Models by developing a predictive understanding of carbon-rich Arctic ecosystems and feedbacks to climate. NGEE Arctic was supported by the Department of Energy's Office of Biological and Environmental Research.

The NGEE Arctic project had two field research sites: 1) located within the Arctic polygonal tundra coastal region on the Barrow Environmental Observatory (BEO) and the North Slope near Utqiagvik (Barrow), Alaska and 2) multiple areas on the discontinuous permafrost region of the Seward Peninsula north of Nome, Alaska.

Through observations, experiments, and synthesis with existing datasets, NGEE Arctic provided an enhanced knowledge base for multi-scale modeling and contributed to improved process representation at global pan-Arctic scales within the Department of Energy's Earth system Model (the Energy Exascale Earth System Model, or E3SM), and specifically within the E3SM Land Model component (ELM).

Data Characteristics**Study Areas**

The first study area is located in the Sagavanirktok (Sag) River basin, located on the North Slope of Alaska (Figure 1a). Meteorological forcing data for this region are sourced from the Daymet version 4 dataset (Thornton et al., 2020). Temperatures range from -25°C in January to 15°C in July, with approximately half of the annual precipitation occurring as snowfall from September through April, while summer rainfall contributes around 50 % of the total precipitation. The soil properties used in this study are based on previous modeling efforts and include two primary layers: an organic-rich surface layer (10–30 cm thick) composed of mosses, peats, and organic-rich soils, and the underlying mineral soil layer. For further details on ATS mesh generation, boundary conditions, model setup, and initialization, refer to Jan et al. (2020), Gao & Coon (2022), and Coon et al. (2022).

In this study, we randomly selected 22 hillslopes, each parameterized based on sub-catchments within the Sag River basin. These hillslopes span a range of slopes and drainage areas, providing a basis for sensitivity analysis and model development. The 2D variable width hillslopes were derived by downscaling the corresponding 3D sub-catchments through a series of parameterization steps.

The second study area is the Teller watershed, a 2.5 km² drainage basin located approximately 27 miles from Nome on Teller Highway, located on the Seward Peninsula of Alaska (hereafter referred to as Teller27, Figure 1b). Compared to the cold and dry climate of the Sag River basin, the Teller27 site experiences a warmer and wetter climate. The Sag site receives over twice the annual snowfall of Teller27, while the Teller27 site is 7–8°C warmer on average (Gao & Coon, 2022). The Teller27 site was used to evaluate the adjusted runoff coefficients derived from ATS-calibrated simulations in the Sag River basin. The Sag coefficients were implemented into ELM's source code and tested for transferability by applying them in ELM simulations at Teller27. Unlike the Sag River analysis, no ATS simulations were used at Teller27; instead, ELM performance was evaluated directly against observed streamflow data.

ATS Model

ATS solves integrated surface/subsurface flow in complex topographic landscape with complex soil structures, which can capture a wide array of processes and their interactions to produce a holistic system understanding of a system (Painter et al., 2016; Coon et al., 2020; Gao & Coon, 2022). As a physics-rich hydrological model, ATS uses physically based representations for surface runoff, subsurface runoff, and river routing. Please see the paper for further details on the ATS governing equations considered in this work.

ELM Model

The runoff parameterization within ELM is designed to represent how water moves across the land surface between grid cells and is influenced by numerous factors, including soil moisture, topography, vegetation cover, etc. ELM's runoff scheme (ported from CLM v4.5, Oleson et al., 2013) is based on a simple TOPMODEL-based concept with a simplified topography representation (Niu et al., 2005). The runoff in ELM is partitioned into surface and subsurface flows, both of which are assumed to be related to water storage, vertical infiltration, and groundwater-soil water interactions (Beven & Kirkby, 1979; Niu et al., 2005, 2007). There are more than twenty runoff components (variables) defined in ELM, but basically, they can be

categorized into three groups in a simulation with fixed land use: i) surface runoff, ii) subsurface runoff, and iii) runoff from overland water bodies like wetlands, lakes, and glaciers. The top 10 layers are considered soil to a depth of ~ 3.8 m and are hydrologically and biogeochemical active. The remaining 5 ground layers in each column are considered to be dry bedrock that extend to a depth of ~ 42.1 m. Here, we only explicitly list the key equations representing the crucial components of the former two groups representing for surface/subsurface runoff; for a more detailed description of the underlying physics and complete formulations, readers are referred to existing literature (Oleson et al., 2013; Niu et al., 2005; Bisht et al., 2018; Liao et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Map of the a) Teller27 and the b) Sag River sites and inset map of Alaska with sites indicated with red boxes. Detailed site maps a) and b) include watershed boundaries (red), rivers (blue), Sag River hillslopes (white dots, 22), and the Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) for each site. The 2.5 km² Teller27 site, being much smaller and with much more limited elevational range than the Sag River site, is 10 times smaller than the Sag River basin elevational range (see legend). Sag hillslopes (22) are not found on the lower elevation North Slope coastal plain, below 250 m.

The ELM model was implemented at 0.5-degree resolution of subgrid-scale surface/land use input parameters and driven by ERA5-Land meteorological forcings (Muñoz-Sabater et al., 2021). We used the Offline Land Model Testbed (OLMT) to standardize ELM case setup and model spin-up (e.g., Sinha et al., 2023). Model spin-up proceeds through two phases after Thornton & Rosenbloom (2005): the first phase features accelerated biogeochemical cycling

while the second phase uses standard biogeochemical reaction rates. These spin-up phases are run for 260 and 200 years, respectively, to ensure vegetation and biogeochemistry has approached a steady-state condition before beginning a transient run that spans 1850-2024.

Please see the paper for further details on the ELM simulations and runoff generation.

Streamflow Measurements

Streamflow measurements were collected at the Teller27 watershed river outlet (Busey et al., 2019). For additional climate, snow, subsurface properties, and permafrost at the Teller27 site, refer to Bennett et al. (2022), Jafarov et al. (2018), Léger et al. (2019), Thaler et al. (2023), and Wang et al. (2024). To evaluate the influence of soil property parameters on ELM-simulated runoff, a series of parameter sensitivity analyses was conducted. In each simulation, one parameter was perturbed by $\pm 50\%$ from its default average value (ELM's surface and land use files are extracted from the global 0.5-degree resolution files), while the values of all other parameters were fixed.

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